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以教授電影製作作為一種在世存有的方法
Teaching filmmaking as a way of being-in-the-world

TORRES PEREZ, Santiago

Graduate Student, International Master of the Arts Program in Cultural and Creative
Industries/Taipei National University of the Arts
Professor, Escuela Nacional de Artes Cinematográficas/Universidad Nacional
Autónoma de México

摘要

Abstract

The philosopher Vilém Flusser characterizes the widespread use of technical images as a cultural shift equal in importance to the introduction of the written word during the neolithic. Even though cinema, one of the leading forms of technical image, has shaped our collective perception for over a century, and has caused major ontological and epistemological breakthroughs in contemporary philosophy most universities study and teach cinema in a very narrow way; a craft for the film industry, a tool for contemporary art or a subject of historical and theoretical analysis in the field of film studies.

German Prof. Thomas Elsaesser wrote of the possibility of “living cinema as a particular way of being-in-the-world and participating in its unfolding, its becoming present”(2016), could we possibly teach such a thing through academia?

The American artist and California Institute of the Arts teacher James Benning has been doing it for a few decades, setting an example of a different path for teaching cinema. His class entitled ‘Looking and Listening’ sets the students out of the classroom, making them approach otherness and contemplate with rigorous observation for long periods of time. His teaching style is closely related to his films, made within a very personal methodology that differs greatly in form and content from the Institutional Mode of Representation. By analyzing Benning’s work as a case study for Flusser (1983, 1985) and Elsaesser (2016) theories we could trace a path towards a different pedagogical approach to filmmaking, one of deeper understanding and insight that lead us into ground we have not previously covered.

Keywords: James Benning, filmmaking pedagogy, otherness

Teaching filmmaking as a way of being-in-the-world

Introduction

Movies have changed our understanding and relation to the world. The epistemological consequences of the production of technical images such as film, video and photography have been studied in several fields including philosophy. Even when we know these facts higher education has, almost exclusively, treated the issue of teaching film production as a matter of skill training geared towards the industries that require filmic products.

By using the pedagogic and film practice of James Benning as a case study I will try to make a case of the possibility of gearing the center of attention of teaching films in higher education out of the industry of films and into a search for meaning and understanding.

Figure 1: Ten Skies (Benning 2004). Still from the movie.

There is a common tendency to mistake a cinematographic image with the original phenomenon in front of the camera. As Vilém Flusser (1983) wrote the following:

Human beings forget they created the images in order to orientate themselves in the world. Since they are no longer able to decode them, their lives become

a function of their own images (p. 10)

It is sometimes necessary to be reminded: the image in figure 1 is not a cloud, it is a representation of a cloud. The first line in Vilém Flusser's 1983 book 'Towards Towards a Philosophy of Photography' states that "Images are significant surfaces", they signify in order to make time and space comprehensible to us as abstractions.

Images have a direct effect on us, and Flusser traced a trajectory on the way we have handled these abstractions as perceptual-cultural development with three major revolutions given by the use of three tools: the image, the written word, and the technical image.

Flusser considers each of these cultural shifts equal in importance, the introduction of drawing during prehistory enabled us to depict our perceptions of the world over a surface. The elements contained in that depiction didn't have an order, he gives the example of the sun and a rooster crowing, the sun and the rooster did not have a chronological linearity, it is not definable if the sun is there because of the crowing or if the crowing is present because of the sun. Magical relations were encouraged by thinking in those terms.

During the neolithic something changed, with the invention of written language there was a vectorization of discourse, linearity and causality became part of how we understood the world. How the written language changed humankind was this second revolution in how we make abstractions of time and space into a surface. The linearization of history, and the constant look for cause and effect are part of that epistemological development.

During the nineteenth century, after the industrial revolution we changed again with the inception of technical images. We developed programs and constituted them into mechanical or electronic machines, these machines by its programming in turn caused a new kind of image, the technical image.

It is not the result of lines drawn over a surface, it is the result of an infinitesimal array of dots, that show the result of the program of the machine. In photography and film they were first silver particles oxidized and developed, now the majority of these technical images are made out of a reticle of pixels.

Film is one of the main types of technical image. Unlike photography it linearizes discourse. The optical acquisition of the light thru the lens, and the illusion of movement obscure the process, the apparatus, the program. Film for seems to be transparent and that transparency hides a lot of differentiated facts:

It seems to present a direct representation, instead of a complex program, what we see is not an image that the author directly passed by its perception, and then coded an image following a set of cultural norms, as would a painting or a poem. It is a technical image it represents a series of ideas mechanically, digitally and optically put together into a series of infinitesimal dots, that seem like a sort of objective representation of what it is in front of the camera.

It seems like time and space are presented instead of represented.

Furthermore, it appears like there wasn't an author with a point of view, and that each shot has been trimmed, composed, exposed, color corrected.

It hides the fact that an entire industry is behind the mere possibility of a spectator watching the resulting film, and other industries are needed for the apparatus needed for image acquisition.

In every film we watch, in every shot, we can study all those elements, some are recorded -how an individual pointed the camera, in a specific way, with a determined goal, reaching toward otherness, a phenomena of interest-, and some are part of the exhibition -how the audience experiences the film, the technology required in order to be shown, the specific duration and space needed.

Film form is very powerful, electric shadows seem to bring back to life a meaningful instant, be it our ancestors when they were still alive, or a carefully placed arrangement of objects that are made to look like something else entirely. Life captured gets another chance to be re-integrated into the flow of time, even if it's only its sound and light the transparency of the medium is powerful enough to make us forget for a while.

A constant influx of technical images reaches us daily. Sometimes we question those images, most of the time we don't. The producers of technical images, like the photographers and filmmakers are at the forefront of this cultural shift. Producers try to get images for which the programs were not designed, leading to new forms, or alterations. New knowledge is being produced.

If we take these facts into consideration, we should start treating film production more seriously, and filmmaking as a real possibility towards new philosophical knowledge. We could search for an ontological change for the filmmaking practice that leads towards what Thomas Elsaesser (2016) calls "living cinema as a particular way of being-in-the-world", not as craftsmen developing storytelling devices, but as thinkers with the tools of our time.

Research questions

To go forward I would like to answer to research questions

- a) What are we teaching in film schools?
- b) How could we teach filmmaking as a meaning-making machine?

What are we teaching in film schools?

The American Film Institute (AFI) ranks among the top film schools both by industry publications such as The Hollywood Reporter or Variety, and also by sites such as topuniversities.com (I had trouble trying to find more authoritative academic rankings)

The institution web-page hosts its (*AFI CONSERVATORY LEARNING OUTCOMES*, n.d.) for the students enrolled in its graduate film directing 'AFI Conservatory' as:

Narrative Structure:

To learn the elements of dramatic structure. To understand and articulate the turning points of story. To create and maintain narrative momentum throughout a film, beginning, middle and end.

Visual Storytelling

To learn and practice the language of visual

storytelling, using action, performance and the camera to convey information, emotion and drama. To stage and shoot with an emphasis on character objectives and on narrative point of view.

Collaboration with Actors

To learn how to cast and work effectively with actors in order to elicit the best possible performance.

Collaboration with Production Team

To learn how to collaborate effectively and lead with Producers, Cinematographers, Editors, Production Designer, and Screenwriters and other key crew members in an effort to realize the story's intentions.

Storytelling, collaboration with peers and best practices within the film industry seem to be the focal point.

One of the leading Documentary Film graduate programs is offered at UK's National Film and Television School (NFTS), as we can see in Figure 2 storytelling skills and industry integration are some of the characteristics that the institution itself values the most, by highlighting its association with BBC and Screen Skills, famous guest speakers and award winning alumni and faculty. There is an implicit promise in some of the websites of a future professional career at the highest levels of the industry, as shown at most of this sites, Czech Republic's Film and TV School of the Academy of Performing Arts in Prague (FAMU) acknowledges the five American Academy Awards (Oscars) its alumni have won, Beijing Film Academy shows photos of their well known directors.

I researched at least the top 20 institutions related to film making programs and only in the documentary programs were there mentions of social issues such as Stanford's "The philosophy of the program is predicated on a paradigm of independent media that values artistic expression, aesthetics, social awareness, and an articulated perspective", but the curricula might only reflect those differences with some optative courses.

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Directing Documentary Masters

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Overview

In partnership with **BBC Documentaries** **BBC STUDIOS**

This course aims to give students the tools and the confidence to become successful documentary makers. We put storytelling at the centre of the filmmaking process, while at the same time encouraging each student to experiment and develop their personal voice.

Our students are regularly nominated for, and win, prestigious prizes around the world. In recent years they have been consistent winners at the Grierson Awards, as well as Sheffield DocFest, BAFTA, Student Academy Awards, Royal Television Society, Hot Docs, Poitiers and many others.

Students collaborate with students in other specialisms to make several films and participate in practical projects, developing the vital skills of both directing and collaboration. All production costs are met by the School.

All NFTS students can attend **Masterclasses**. Recent guests include David Fincher (*Fight Club*), Greta Gerwig (*Little Women*), Steve McQueen (*12 Years A Slave*), Edgar Wright (*Hot Fuzz*), Phoebe Waller-Bridge (*Fleabag*), Ben Wheatley (*Free Fire*), Rapman (*Blue Story*), Louis Theroux, Debra Granik (*Winter's Bone*), Denis Villeneuve (*Bladerunner 2049*), Lynne Ramsay (*You Were Never Really Here*), Sam Mendes (*1917*), Asif Kapadia (*Senna*), Joanna Hogg (*The Souvenir*), Russell T Davies (*Doctor Who*) and Alex Gibney (*Citizen K*).

Head of Department Peter Dale won a 2019 BAFTA for his work on Louis Theroux: *Altered States*.

ScreenSkills Select This course is industry recognised by ScreenSkills, the industry-led skills body for the UK's screen-based industries, and carries the ScreenSkills Select quality-mark which indicates courses best suited to prepare students for a career in the screen industries.

Figure 2: NFTS Directing documentary overview

Epistemological values don't seem to be the main concern. There is a page at NFTS website called 'Value for Money' aimed to their potential students (or their parents) to let them know what they will get:

Value For Money

At the National Film and Television School we offer practical, hands-on teaching from industry professionals, using industry-standard film and television stages and high-quality equipment to enable our students to make high-quality films, television shows, games and other projects. The School meets all production costs, and our students win awards and compete at festivals around the world. Our 38-week teaching year and our intensive approach to teaching and learning means MA and Diploma students get far more tuition time than the vast majority of postgraduate institutions offer.

All NFTS students have access to our masterclasses programme of high profile speakers from across the film, television and games industries and many of our MA and Diploma courses include work placements at prominent industry companies. Our Bridges to Industry programme also gives students the opportunity to work on extracurricular projects with commercial partners.

We are also the only UK film School that appears consistently in the global Hollywood Reporter listing of the top 20 International Film Schools.

At least from what can be seen from their self published material, and maybe with just more than marketing purposes it seem that film schools take only a small part of all the elements mentioned in the introduction into consideration.

An emphasis on narrative storytelling is present in most fiction and non-fiction curricula. It is not difficult to see how this is related to the linearization that Flusser characterizes as a meaningful part of written language. At a deeper level we can see that the type of storytelling commonly taught at film schools is set on a main character, with a specific goal, forces opposed to that goal, allies to help them realize it, and a specific structure that the narration has to go through in a series of causes and effects that result in the transformation of the character because of the journey. In non-fiction films in order for this kind of narration to make sense complex individuals with multiple goals, without a lineal path, get to be transformed into characters, with one main goal.

I understand how film schools work quite well since I have been a teacher for more than thirteen years. I started to teach even before my graduation, my main concern back then was geared towards sharing the craft to aspiring filmmakers. That aim reflected my own search into becoming a professional documentary director and cinematographer. As I got comfortable with my practice, my main goal was to let the students see the way ahead more clearly. If I could let them know how to manage the initial steps of their career better than I did that would mean they potentially didn't had to spend as long as it did for me. Probably the intention was to treat them as if I was teaching myself.

Time went on and I became aware of something much more important than how to do the work, it was why I decided to do it in the first place.

We film what we are curious about, what we care, what makes us feel a certain way. In order to make someone else part of that. So the question is:

How could we teach filmmaking as a meaning-making machine?

Inside the California Institute of the Arts (CalArts) one of the high ranking film schools among the ones mentioned previously in this paper, Professor James Benning has been teaching uninterruptedly since 1987, each year from 1987 to 2012 he used to teach a course called 'Looking and Listening'. The course description in their curricula was the following:

FPFV-456 Listening/Seeing (4 Credits)

Each week a different location (either urban, rural, or wilderness) will be visited for the purposes of listening and seeing. At the end of the visit the class will meet within the location to discuss what each has individually experienced. Attention will be given to how the experiences of listening and looking can translate into the making of images and sound. A written journal is required to document what has been heard and seen, and each student will be required to do extensive research on one of the locations visited. Some of the specific sites are: an oilfield, emergency hospital waiting room, Death Valley, the Los Angeles Port in Long Beach, San Fernando Road, and 29 Palms military base. (CalArts, n.d.)

To describe Benning's own work we can reference back to the cloud in figure 1, the still frame from the movie 'Ten Skies' (2004). James Benning is an established director of formalist, avant-garde films with a career spanning from the mid-1970's until today. 'Ten Skies' is 97 minutes long, during that time we get to see ten fixed shots of the sky, and drifting clouds going by. Some movies can be spoiled by revealing the turning points of their plot, but some of Benning's films can be summarized with their brief titles, such as 'Thirteen Lakes', '20 cigarettes' or '10 skies'. Some of his films might be conceptual, but their core interests lie elsewhere,

and it is usually right in front of us, in the image, on the surface, along the duration. His films force the audience to observe phenomena that they might have taken for granted even if they were present during the shooting of the film.

Benning's seemingly detached observational films, come from an attitude within himself that also reflects the way he teaches, as he tells in an interview (Zuvela, 2004):

I used to think you couldn't teach someone to become an artist – they either were or they weren't. I think now that you can provide basic training, starting with teaching how to listen and how to look – learn the basics of how hard it is to pay attention. Mine [teaching classes] are kind of like performance classes where the students become active viewers. We go on excursions, and they do it, the students, they show up at 4am, and we'll go down a mountain road in the dark and go to the top of a hill. Gradually, as it gets more and more light, they'll look around and they'll realise that we're in a place where a forest fire had been... they become aware of a change in sounds, sights...it's about the articulation of change, the little subtle changes that take place over time, watching the sun come up. I try to get them to pay attention, and they appreciate it.

The point of it is not to translate that immediately into art, either, but to think about seeing. The students are enthusiastic and these are very successful classes. I'm most proud of going against my own conviction that you can't teach art. Their success as artists makes me very proud.

At another interview (MacDonald, 2007) Benning described an artist as someone who pays attention and report back. Both his films and his classes are about practicing attention, for him as a filmmaker and for us as audience. His methodology does something quite different than traditional filmmaking or teaching, and it is very simple;

a) In his classes:

students are required to go somewhere they don't know,

students are given a long period of time to observe, feel and think about their perceptions,

students are not required to produce something right away,

students are encouraged to report back to the group.

b) In his films:

He is required to approach a phenomena he is interested about, then he gives himself a long period of time to observe, feel and then think about his perceptions,

he does not go with a camera during the periods of observation, so he isn't pressured to film right away.

This atypical methodology lets their students be right there, right now. Approaching otherness, being confronted with phenomena beyond their control. Living filmmaking this way makes you get close to others, be it the ones in your group that shared a moment that might get to be meaningful, close to those 'other' that you are approaching during your observation and filming, and closer too to the audience that is experiencing an observation of their own. But the audience (if they engage) now also has discovered that you have also filmed your decisions, on how to report those observations, the student/the filmmaker is now accountable for those decisions.

When it is time to set the camera, it suddenly means something where and why you cut, how you frame. Benning himself described it the following way:

Because the biggest manipulation is the frame, and what you leave out and how you take everything else out of context by taking just the small portion of the world. And therefore it's silly to talk about 'complete reality'. It's always your point of view what you leave out and where you point the camera... A lot of people want my films to be that, but they've never been that. They've always been a selection, always been colour-corrected, always been highly manipulated with sound. They've always taken a real point of view from what I believe in, and I am full of prejudice. And those prejudices are on the screen.(Bradshaw, 2013)

Benning acknowledges the traces of manipulation that can help us reverse engineer the relation between filmmaker, camera and subject. His treatment of the

image is that of a significant surface that has been imprinted by his own decisions, even if most of the work has been produced by the program of the capture device.

In a conversation with Richard Linklater (Klinger, 2014) Benning mentions that he is not interested in his student making good movies as there are a lot of those already and he states that his real interest is for their student to find “a new language, a new way of working, of pushing the film culture grow”.

Going back to *Ten Skies* this is how Benning thought about it (Zuvela, 2004):

Now I'm working on *Ten Skies*, which will be ten shots of sky, using a normal lens. I had a look at some of the shots and it really got the detail, I didn't think it would but it really did. The funny thing is because of the shape of the frame, it's kind of like looking at the sky through the sunroof of a car! I'm really interested in the ways the sky changes in reaction to the landscape below – how the clouds look above the mountains, over flat lands, above a forest fire, which was kind of creating its own weather system... There's this one shot where these two white clouds are in the frame and then this black cloud from behind comes up and covers the whole frame – it makes a wipe! The whole thing is very dramatic, and it's just cloud movement.

All the shots end up with a dynamic quality, I never saw that before, I never had the courage. It took me 50 years to look at the sky like that! I call it “found paintings”. I think of my landscape works now as anti-war artworks – they're about the antithesis of war, the kind of beauty we're destroying. The *Ten Skies* works came about because I'm thinking about what the opposite of war was.

We can watch a film consisting of ten fixed shots of the sky and think about it as an exercise of self indulgence or as an antiwar film that gives us the opportunity to look back at our sky in a different way. That is something the camera program did not intended to do, using Flusser's terms he is smuggling human intentions into a program in a way that is not predicted by it.

Something much more important than teaching how to do the work, is why to do it in the first place. Why we take the camera in the first place.

In a preliminary sketch to his 1579 book ‘*The Ascent to Mount Carmel*’ mystical

Spanish writer St. John of the Cross wrote “to come to what you don't know you have to go where you don't know”.

Making non-fiction as a way of life has meant for me to regularly set yourself in situations that are unknown in order to understand, or more importantly to put yourself in the presence of others, distant from what you know and being changed in the process.

There are of course problems with this approach,

1- It has security and health risks

Being away of the campus, doing field work in the areas selected for observation became an increasing preoccupation for the university as Benning commented on an interview when asked about the class(Bradshaw, 2013):

I stopped. For a number of reasons, mainly that there are too many lawyers in the world and the school's nervous. Their solution was a lot of restrictions on what I could do, and things that would make the school not liable but nothing to make me not liable. That pissed me off.

I love CalArts, but it's become an institution now, because of the pressure of outside agencies that want to regulate what we do. I don't think any of the art schools in the US have gotten together to fight this interference to regulate the way art is taught and quantify everything and prove that you're doing this. It's all dumb stuff because it comes from other models and you don't teach art that way. Hopefully the pendulum will swing against it, but it's way too corporate for me.

And this is the school that was built against all those things. In the classroom it actually still functions the way it always did: we get really good students and good work; I'm inspired. And the diversity is increasing. It's not quite there for income level but it certainly is for different colours, religious backgrounds and sexual preferences. It's a utopian situation with the problems of trying to remain utopian, because the outside world comes in; we all live and come from it. But those are problems I like to negotiate, rather than these corporate problems of law and being afraid of being sued.

2- It does not fit academic structures

Usual semester terms are sixteen to eighteen weeks long, each class set to an assigned number of hours a week. Long classes are hardly encouraged.

3- The alumni would have basically no guaranteed income after the end of the program

The usual advertising grabs for film school would not be available to a practitioner of this kind of film making.

Apart from Looking and listening Another aspect of Benning's style of teaching can be found in the methodology he uses to develop new films, or it can be even claimed by the lack of such methodology. Instead of going in the traditional route of writing a proposal, developing it into a script, establishing a crew, securing funding, promoting it in film festivals, getting an international sales agent and distributing in film theaters commercially, Benning gives across the impression of an art practice that is an organic outgrow of his life. One example of how he teaches this approach are his lectures and interviews.

Apart from his regular courses, Benning gives lectures in other universities. I will describe a conference given by James Benning in October 2014 at UCLA's Hammer Museum; the structure and the content of this lecture does not follow the traditional means associated with a graduate level conference.

It starts as an ordinary academic endeavor, with a brief introduction of Benning by a presenter, and Benning proceeding to show the desktop of his laptop on a big screen. He opens and plays a DVD of one of his films, shot on the streets of the city where he grew up. Up to this point nothing is out of the ordinary, but the next twenty minutes at first do not seem to make much sense, as he opens Google maps, and shows the exact location of his childhood home, first in satellite and then on street view. He takes time to show the baseball field across the street where he spend 'years of his life'. He zooms out of his childhood neighborhood in Michigan, changes states south west into California, zooms in at the Sierra Nevada Mountains until he reached a satellite view of his current home, as there is no no street view of his home, he opens Facebook, searches himself and navigates along his profile until he opens a photograph showing an outside view of his home, there is recently washed laundry set to dry on the front porch of a two story house surrounded by a forest. He spend some

time talking about the renovations he did himself to the property when he bought it several years prior.

He states that after finishing the renovations on his house he needed something else to do and started to copy American Folk paintings made by Bill Taylor. He copied dozens of his pictures, but felt the need to keep building, so he set himself to build a replica of the cabin in which Henry David Thoreau's wrote the book 'Walden; or, Life in the Woods'. He spends a few minutes talking about details of the construction of the exterior, interior, replicas of furniture, lists of books and paintings that he put inside the cabin, and when he finished he still felt the need to keep building and made a replica of the infamous cabin of the domestic American terrorist Theodore John Kaczynski also known as the Unabomber. Benning goes into detail again about the cabin, the interior, the books that he shared with the Unabomber as both of them studied mathematics, and finally he talks about his correspondence with Kaczynski.

He allegedly built both cabins with no purpose in mind. At this point of the lecture Benning goes back to google maps and shows both cabins in his property. Then he slowly starts to list and describe all the works associated with his 'Two Cabins project', it includes a book called 'Two Cabins' (2011) -with photographs of the cabins, writings by him and other authors-, the films 'Stample pass' (2012) and 'Two cabins' (2011) and ultimately and the exhibition 'Decoding Fear' took place at Kunsthaus Graz, in Graz, Austria from March 7 until June 1, 2014 and was curated by Peter Pakesch, showing multiple installations, copies of Bill Taylor's paintings, copies of the correspondence between Benning and the Unabomber.

He presented himself as a filmmaker being-in-the-world and generally speaking found a way of teaching being-in-the-world for filmmakers. Benning might shine a light on how to teach filmmaking as a meaning making machine, and he at least is a great example to follow or to inspire a coherent methodology from.

Each culture has dealt very differently with the advent of Flusser's breaking points. Cultures used to be totally or partially disconnected by geography. Their own experiences of space and place influenced their images, written language, but in a globalized world technical images add a layer of complexity. Technical images world

wide are made with technology made in just a couple of countries. The standard modes of representation (Burch, 1990), for example Hollywood style of film making (Bordwell, 2006; Bordwell et al., 2003) , are rooted in values aligned in the favor of colonial tough (that would need a conference in itself). Most importantly the programs inside our cameras, and other technical devices are also created in just a couple of countries.

Having a deep understanding of filmmaking as a tool for making new knowledge, and developing local pedagogical methods is an urgent task for countries of the global south. Our images are not seen as often, so they don't have the same influence as those that are constantly shown. Images shape our world and our conscience, developing our own set of tools.

Conclusion

By analyzing Benning's work as a case study for Flusser and Elsaesser theories we could trace a path towards a different pedagogical approach to filmmaking, one of deeper understanding and insight that lead us into ground we have not previously covered.

Bibliography

- AFI CONSERVATORY LEARNING OUTCOMES*. (n.d.). AFI CONSERVATORY.
Retrieved October 28, 2022, from <https://conservatory.afi.com/learning-outcomes/>
- Bordwell, D. (2006). *The Way Hollywood Tells It: Story and Style in Modern Movies*. In *The Way Hollywood Tells It*. University of California Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1525/9780520932326>
- Bordwell, D., Staiger, J., & Thompson, K. (2003). *The Classical Hollywood Cinema: Film Style and Mode of Production to 1960*. Routledge.
- Bradshaw, N. (2013, October). The Sight & Sound Interview: James Benning. *Sight and Sound*, 23(10), 46–50.
- Burch, N. (1990). *Life to Those Shadows*. University of California Press.
- CalArts. (n.d.). *Course Catalog—CalArts Self Service*. Retrieved November 18, 2022, from <https://selfservice.calarts.edu/Student/Courses/Search?keyword=looking+and+listening>
- Elsaesser, T. (2016). *Film history as media archaeology*. Amsterdam University Press.
- Flusser, V. (1983). *Towards a philosophy of photography*. Reaktion Books.
- Flusser, V. (1985). *Into the universe of technical images* (Vol. 32). U of Minnesota press.
- Klinger, G. (Director). (2014, March). *Double Play: James Benning et Richard Linklater*. In *Cinéma, de notre temps*.
- MacDonald, S. (2007, September). TESTING YOUR PATIENCE: AN INTERVIEW WITH JAMES BENNING. *Artforum*, 46(1).
<https://www.artforum.com/print/200707/testing-your-patience-an-interview-with-james-benning-15707>

Zuvela, D. (2004). Talking About Seeing: A Conversation with James Benning –
Senses of Cinema. *Senses of Cinema*, 33.

http://www.sensesofcinema.com/2004/the-suspended-narrative/james_benning

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